
IMPLICATIONS OF FUEL SUBSIDY REMOVAL ON HOUSEHOLD INCOME AND STANDARD OF LIVING IN BAYELSA STATE

By

Ogbomah, Oyin-Emi Frank – Bayelsa State Polytechnic Aleibiri, Bayelsa State, Nigeria.
(Ogbomahfrank11@gmail.com)

Kolokolo Francis – Bayelsa State Polytechnic Aleibiri, Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Abstract

This research investigates the effects of petrol subsidy removal on household income and the standard of living in Bayelsa State. Petrol subsidy removal in Nigeria has sparked extensive debates among political analysts and economists since the return of civil rule in 1999. Attempts by previous administrations to eliminate fuel subsidy have been met with strong opposition from labour unions and civil society organizations. The government's justification for removing the fuel subsidy centers on the assertion that it strains government finances. On May 29, 2023, President Ahmed Bola Tinubu announced the removal of the fuel subsidy during his inaugural speech, which resulted in an unprecedented increase in transportation fares, food prices, and the overall cost of goods and services in the country. Thus, this study examines the potential effects of fuel subsidy removal on households in Bayelsa State. The study utilized the descriptive survey research design. Questionnaires and oral interviews were used to collect the primary data from residents in Yenagoa and Sagbama Local Government Areas of Bayelsa State. Out of 300 distributed questionnaires to the target population, 220 were returned. The arithmetic mean was used to analyze the data collected. The findings indicate that the removal of the fuel subsidy has negatively impacted the purchasing power of many households as well as the standard of living in Bayelsa State. The study recommends, among other things, the implementation of monthly cash transfers to vulnerable people, and the provision of subsidized public transportation system in the country to cushion the impact of fuel subsidy removal.

Keywords: *Fuel Subsidy, Subsidy Removal, Household Income, Standard of Living.*

Introduction

Fuel subsidy in Nigeria has been one of the most contentious and debated issues for several decades. The petroleum subsidy can be traced back to the 1970s during the military era. The introduction of fuel subsidy by the military government in 1970s was a short-term measure to cushion the effects of rising international oil prices. Initially, fuel subsidies during the 1970s were intended as a temporary fiscal response to the increase in crude oil prices instigated by the Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC), but they have been retained by subsequent Nigerian governments as a mechanism for stabilizing domestic fuel prices and providing economic benefits to the people (IISD, 2016).

While the initial intention of the fuel subsidy was to make petroleum products affordable to Nigerians at a price below the market rate, thus reducing the financial burden on citizens, it has now become a burden to the government. This is due to the fact that budgetary allocations for petroleum subsidy have continued to increase on a yearly basis, making it difficult for the government to sustain the subsidy on petroleum products. Between 2005 and 2022, the Federal Government spent a staggering sum of \$84.39 billion to subsidize fuel in the country. This figure indicates that the subsidy on petrol consumed over 70 percent of potential Federal Government revenue, pushing the country to the brink of bankruptcy (Udeme, 2025).

To lessen the financial burden of fuel subsidy on the government, successive governments since 1999 have adopted gradual upward adjustments of petrol prices. These increments have always faced resistance from labour unions, particularly the Nigerian Labour Congress, and civil society organizations in the country. For example, when former President Goodluck Jonathan removed the fuel subsidy on January 1, 2012, increasing the petrol price from N65 to N141, it resulted in a nationwide strike organized by labor unions (Oyetunde, 2012).

In addition to the nationwide strike in January 2012, there were massive protests and demonstrations against the removal of the fuel subsidy across major cities in Nigeria, tagged "Occupy Nigeria." Civil society organizations and professional bodies, such as the Nigeria Bar Association (NBA) and the Committee for the Defense of Human Rights (CDHR), as well as eminent Nigerians like Ahmed Bola Tinubu and Muhammadu Buhari, joined the protests (Adeyemi, 2012; Amaize et al., 2012). The direct effect of the 2012 protests and the nationwide strike was the reinstatement of the fuel subsidy, as the Federal Government reduced the fuel price from N141 to N97.

The outright removal of the fuel subsidy on May 29, 2023, by President Bola Ahmed Tinubu took everyone by surprise. While the three major presidential aspirants in the 2023 general elections Alhaji Atiku Abubakar of the People's Democratic Party (PDP), Mr. Peter Obi of the Labour Party, and Ahmed Bola Tinubu of the All Progressives Congress (APC) stated during their campaigns that they would remove the fuel subsidy if elected, it was President Bola Ahmed Tinubu's sudden announcement during his inaugural speech that truly caught everyone off guard.

The announcement of the fuel subsidy removal in 2023 caused widespread apprehension throughout the country, as fuel stations quickly adjusted their pump prices. By 2024, petrol was being sold at N1,300 per liter. The sudden increase in fuel prices led to hikes in transportation, foodstuff, goods and services etc. across the country (Edu et al., 2023; Okerinde, 2023; Akpan et al., 2024).

In light of these effects, this study seeks to explore how the increase in petrol prices has impacted household income and the standard of living in Bayelsa State.

Statement of the problem

The removal of fuel subsidies in Nigeria has generated a lot of controversy, given the high level of poverty in the country. Historically, fuel subsidies were aimed at reducing the financial burden on vulnerable members of society in light of the volatility of fuel prices in the international market. Thus, the fuel subsidy helped ensure that citizens had access to affordable transportation and energy. However, the complete removal of fuel subsidies by the Nigerian government poses significant challenges for those who are vulnerable. An increase in fuel prices will directly affect the cost of living and, by extension, the purchasing power of workers and businesses in the country (Ogunfowora, 2022).

In Bayelsa State, where a large portion of the population already struggles with economic hardship and relies on meager incomes, the implications of the removal of fuel subsidies will strain household finances and may further exacerbate the already high levels of poverty in the state (Ajayi, 2023). The increase in transportation costs and the prices of foodstuffs, goods, and services resulting from the removal of fuel subsidies will undoubtedly reduce disposable income, thereby limiting the funds available for families to meet their basic needs (Nwankwo, 2023).

Furthermore, this situation may exacerbate social vices in the state, such as armed robbery and kidnapping, as families struggle to cope with the economic pressures caused by the removal of fuel subsidies. This study, therefore, examines the potential impact of the removal of fuel subsidies on household income and the standard of living in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

- (i) How does the removal of fuel subsidy affect households' income and the standard of living in Bayelsa State?
- (ii) What strategies are households in Bayelsa State adopting to cope with the economic hardship caused by the removal of the fuel subsidy?
- (iii) What are the measures taken by the government to cushion the impact of fuel subsidy removal on households in Bayelsa State?

Objectives of the Study

The study is aimed to achieve the following objectives:

- (i) to examine the effect of petrol subsidy removal on household income and the standard of living in Bayelsa State
- (ii) to examine the strategies adopted by households in Bayelsa State to cope with the economic hardship caused by the removal of the fuel subsidy?
- (iii) to identify measures taken by the government to cushion the impact of fuel subsidy removal in Bayelsa State.

CONCEPTUAL REVIEW/THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Subsidy

Subsidy is derived from the Latin word “subsidiium,” which means support, assistance, aid, help, and protection. In medieval times, it referred to payments made to the king (Steenblick, 2006). Although the term has evolved from its traditional definition to encompass a broader meaning, the practices of royalty receiving subsidies have not ceased. For instance, in 2004, the Queen of England and the Duke of Westminster received half a million pounds sterling in farm subsidies (Steenblick, 2006).

By definition, a subsidy is any government assistance that (i) enables consumers to purchase goods and services at prices lower than those offered by a perfectly competitive private sector, or (ii) raises producers' incomes beyond what would be earned without this intervention (Schwartz & Clements, 1999).

Adebiyi (2011), in Onyeizugbe and Onwuka (2012), noted that subsidy encompasses any measure that keeps the prices consumers pay for goods or products below market levels, either for consumers or for producers. They stated that subsidies can take various forms, including those that have a direct impact on prices such as grants, tax reductions, exemptions, or price controls. Others may affect prices or costs indirectly, such as regulations that skew the market in favor of a particular fuel or government-sponsored technology and research and development.

The foregoing discussion shows that goods and services that are subsidized do not reflect actual market prices. This indicates that the government is covering the difference in the prices of the subsidized goods or services. Furthermore, subsidies encompass a wide range of areas, including cash transfers, subsidies on goods, food, agricultural produce, tax concessions, energy, and more.

Fuel Subsidy

Fuel subsidies are government policies that lower the price of fuel for consumers by either reducing taxes on fuel or directly subsidizing its cost. The primary aim of these subsidies is to make energy more affordable and accessible, especially in developing countries where energy poverty can hinder economic growth and the overall standard of living (Kojima & Bacon, 2009).

According to Ori et al. (2023), fuel subsidies refer to government policies that provide financial assistance or other forms of support to reduce the cost of fuel for consumers. This initiative is intended to lower domestic fuel prices, making them more accessible and affordable for Nigerians, thereby stimulating economic activities and reducing poverty in the country.

The World Bank (2021) defines fuel subsidies as government policies that set fuel prices below market levels to support consumers and specific sectors of the economy with the aim of enhancing energy availability and stimulating economic growth. The United Nations Development Programme (2023) notes that fuel subsidies are often employed as a social policy tool in developing countries to alleviate poverty and improve citizens' standards of living by reducing fuel prices for vulnerable populations.

In summary, fuel subsidies are deliberately designed government policies aimed at making fuel affordable and accessible for vulnerable members of society while enhancing economic growth. Fuel subsidy serve as a social tool used by the government to alleviate poverty and improving the standard of living of the masses by lowering fuel prices below the market benchmark.

Petrol Subsidy in Nigeria

Fuel subsidy in Nigeria dates back to the 1970s when the federal government introduced the subsidy policy as a means of cushioning the impact of rising crude oil prices in the international market, making petroleum products affordable for Nigerians. The subsidy policy became institutionalized in the 1980s with the establishment of the Petroleum Product Pricing and Regulatory Agency (PPPRA). The PPPRA was tasked with regulating the prices of petroleum products in the country (Ori et al., 2023). This means that petrol stations in Nigeria cannot sell above the regulated prices fixed by the PPPRA.

In recent times, the government has argued that the subsidy on petrol has created a huge financial burden and has drained the country's budget, making it no longer feasible to sustain the fuel subsidy policy. According to the Federal Government, between 2005 and 2025, the total amount spent on subsidizing fuel is estimated to exceed 84.39 billion US dollars. The government noted that this amount accounts for over 70 percent of its revenue (Apkan, 2025).

Recent figures on fuel subsidy payments provided by the Federal Government show that the subsidy has strained government finances. For example, in the first quarter of 2023, the landing cost of fuel in Nigeria was between N500 – N600, and petrol was sold at an average of N200. The government was paying an excess of N300 to N400 as a subsidy for every liter of fuel consumed in the country. In 2022, an estimated N2.74 trillion was paid as a fuel subsidy, while revenue from oil in the same year was just over N600 billion. Similarly, the 2023 budget allocated N3.36 trillion for fuel subsidy from January to June 2023, whereas the projected revenue from oil in 2023 was N2.23 trillion (NESG, 2023).

Despite the significant amounts used for subsidizing fuel and the government borrowing to sustain it, attempts by successive governments to remove the fuel subsidy have often placed the government and citizens at a crossroads. Organized labour and the masses have consistently resisted government efforts to remove the subsidy until, in May 2023, President Bola Ahmed Tinubu ultimately removed the subsidy on petrol.

The removal of the fuel subsidy has led to economic hardship in Nigeria, with prices of food items, goods, and services including transportation fares jumping over 100 percent, thus eroding the purchasing power of the masses and the standard of living in the country.

Arguments for Fuel Subsidy in Nigeria

Regardless of the government's position against petrol subsidies in Nigeria, the benefits of fuel subsidies cannot be overlooked. Below are some of the benefits of petrol subsidies in Nigeria:

- (i) **Poverty Alleviation and Welfare Sustenance:** Given the significance of fuel in daily activities in Nigeria, subsidizing fuel makes it affordable and accessible to the poorer segments of society, which helps alleviate poverty and sustain the welfare of the people. A World Bank study titled "Fuel Subsidy and Poverty Reduction" noted that fuel subsidies can be an effective tool to protect the poor from rising energy costs and enhance their welfare (World Bank, 2010). Furthermore, the World Bank pointed out that an additional 7.1 million Nigerians could be pushed into poverty, particularly without measures to mitigate the negative impacts of subsidy removal (Ujah, 2023). This clearly illustrates that fuel subsidies have played a significant role in alleviating poverty and improving the welfare of Nigerians.
- (ii) **Price Stabilization:** Virtually every activity in Nigeria revolves around fuel usage on a daily basis. Farmers rely on fuel for transportation to their farms and to transport their produce to market. Small like business also use fuel to power their generator to enhance their business. Thus, fuel subsidies help stabilize the prices of food, goods, and services, contributing to the fight against inflation in the country.
- (iii) **Support and Sustain Industries:** Industries predominantly depend on energy for their operations, including the transportation of raw materials and finished goods, as well as powering electricity-generating plants. Given the inconsistent power supply in the country, fuel subsidies help sustain many industries. In 2024, Vanguard reported that over 50 firms closed down, leading to the loss of over 100,000 jobs. Companies such as Glaxo SmithKline Beecham, Procter & Gamble, Mega Plastic Nigeria Limited, Twinstar Nigeria Limited, Femina Hygienical Products Nigeria Limited, and Linda Manufacturing Company were

among those that shut down. The removal of fuel subsidies, along with other harsh economic policies, were cited as the causes of these shutdowns (Ahiuma, 2024). This clearly demonstrates the important of fuel subsidies in supporting and sustaining industries in Nigeria.

(iv) **Stimulate Economic Growth:** Fuel subsidies help to stimulate economic growth. When fuel is subsidized, it becomes more affordable and accessible to households, businesses, and industries, thereby stimulating economic activity. This can enhance household income and improve living standards in the country. Onuoha (2017) noted that fuel subsidies in Nigeria are necessary for economic growth and development. He suggested that instead of outright removal of the subsidy on petrol, the government should focus on eliminating corruption and inefficiencies within the fuel subsidy programme.

Augments Against Fuel Subsidy in Nigeria

Just like there are several benefits to subsidizing petrol products in Nigeria, there are also several arguments in favor of fuel subsidy removal, particularly advanced by the government. Some of the key arguments against fuel subsidy include:

(i) **Strain on Government Finances:** One of the major arguments against fuel subsidy is that it puts pressure on government finances, leading to deficit budgeting over the years. For example, in 2022, N2.74 trillion was paid as fuel subsidy, while the revenue from oil was just over N600 billion. Additionally, in the 2023 budget, N3.36 trillion was allocated for fuel subsidy for the first six months (January to June 2023), whereas the estimated revenue from oil in 2023 was N2.23 trillion (NESG, 2023). This clearly indicates that the government has been borrowing to subsidize fuel for Nigerians, which has negatively impacted government finances.

The removal of fuel subsidy in May 2023 has enhanced revenue for the three tiers of government in the country. In 2023, the 36 states and the 774 local governments received a total of N6.16 trillion as revenue share from the federal government. This figure represents a 28.6 percent increase from the N4.792 trillion received in 2022. Furthermore, the total domestic debt profile of the 36 states and the Federal Capital Territory declined from N5.82 trillion in June 2023 to N3.97 trillion as of December 2024 (Udeme, 2025).

(ii) **Impede Infrastructural Development:** The fuel subsidy policy has negatively affected the provision of infrastructure in critical areas such as health, education, and roads, according to the Federal Government. This is one of the reasons why the Nigerian government has consistently argued for the total removal of fuel subsidy to enable funding for critical infrastructure projects. In 2025, the Federal Government reported it had saved 84 billion USD from the removal of fuel subsidy in 2023. The government further stated that the savings from this removal have been utilized to fund 40 critical roads across the country (Akpan, 2025).

(iii) **Breed Corruption:** Another argument presented by the Federal Government for the removal of the fuel subsidy is that it encourages corruption in the downstream sector of the oil industry. Many payments for fuel subsidies are made for fuel that Nigerians never consumed. For instance, the former Chairman of the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission, Abdulrasheed Bawa, revealed that several oil marketing companies forged documents to illegally access petrol subsidy payments from the government (Aina, 2025). The extensive corruption in subsidy claims and payments was one of the key reasons the government opposes the fuel subsidy.

(iv) **Discourage Investment in the Downstream Sector:** Another reason cited by the government for the removal of fuel subsidy is that it discourages foreign investors from investing in the Nigerian oil industry. The continuous regulation of fuel prices by the government deters private investors, stifles competition, and causes market distortion (Adeleke et al., 2022).

Theoretical Framework

The research is anchored on Public Choice Theory, which has been shaped by prominent theorists like Kenneth Arrow, Duncan Black, Anthony Downs, Mancur Olson, James M. Buchanan, and Gordon Tullock (Parlak & Dogan, 2022). This theory started to take form in the 1950s and gained acceptance during the 1960s, continuing to expand in the 1970s. Gordon Tullock and James M. Buchanan are recognized as the contemporary pioneers of this theory, particularly through their influential work, "The Calculus of Consent." In the early 1960s, while examining the political dimensions of wealth generation and economic development, they proposed the public choice model as a more effective and intellectually robust framework for evaluating public policy (Parlak & Dogan, 2022).

Public choice theory explores how decisions made within public administration, politics, and the economy intersect with the actions of individuals in the field. The theory centers on the behavior of public officials in their decision-making processes, positing that these officials often prioritize their personal gains over the greater public good. It argues that individuals tend not to consider the needs of public institutions and citizens when engaging in political or administrative decisions, focusing instead on fulfilling their own interests (Parlak & Dogan, 2022).

In the context of this study, the removal of the petrol subsidy is seen as contrary to public interest due to the economic hardships it has brought on Nigerians. Thus, from the viewpoint of public choice theory, President Bola Ahmed Tinubu's decision to eliminate the petrol subsidy seems to align more with his personal interests rather than those of the general populace.

Method of the Study

The research adopted the descriptive survey design, utilizing both questionnaires and oral interviews to collect primary data. To ensure that participants clearly understood the study's objectives, purposive sampling was employed. In total, three hundred twenty (320) questionnaires were distributed among residents in Yenagoa and Sagbama Local Government Areas. Out of these, two hundred twenty (220) completed questionnaires were successfully retrieved for analysis.

In addition to the questionnaires, oral interviews were conducted specifically targeting civil servants, labour leaders, farmers and artisans. The purpose of these interviews was to gather more information regarding how fuel subsidy removal affected them. The oral interviews complemented the quantitative data obtained from the questionnaires.

The data collected from the questionnaires were analyzed using the arithmetic mean, allowing for a clearer understanding of the trends and patterns arising from the collected data. The quantitative analysis provided insight into how the removal of the fuel subsidy affected the livelihoods of the respondents.

Findings and Discussion

Table 1: The effect of fuel subsidy removal on households' income and the standard of living in Bayelsa State.

S/N	Items statement	SA (4)	A (3)	D (2)	SD(1)	Total	\bar{x}	Decision
1	Impact household access to essential food items.	120	97	2	1	220		
	Weight of Responses	(480)	(291)	(4)	(1)	776	3.5	Agreed
2	Higher prices for goods and services.	109	107	2	2	220		
	Weight of Responses	(436)	(321)	(4)	(2)	763	3.4	Agreed
3	Erodes the purchasing power of household	115	100	2	3	220		
	Weight of Responses	(460)	(300)	(4)	(3)	767	3.4	Agreed
4	Increased poverty levels	119	97	2	2	220		
	Weight of Responses	(476)	(291)	(4)	(2)	773	3.5	Agreed
	Arithmetic Weighted Mean						3.45	
	Criterion Mean						2.50	

Source: Authors field data, 2024.

The data presented in Table 1 shows that the arithmetic weighted mean of 3.45 is greater than the criterion mean of 2.50. The result shows that the removal of fuel subsidy has resulted in an increase in transportation fare, higher prices of foodstuff, goods and services as well diminish the purchasing power of households in Bayelsa State. Furthermore, the findings show that the removal of fuel subsidy has exacerbated the poverty levels among households in Bayelsa State.

The findings from the questionnaire are in tandem with interviews conducted with several persons in Yenagoa and Sagbama Local Government Areas on the effect of fuel subsidy removal on households' income and the standard of living in Bayelsa State.

The results gathered from the oral interviews indicate that the removal of fuel subsidies has had a detrimental impact on both businesses and household incomes in Bayelsa State. The oral interview revealed that the removal of fuel subsidy has led to major economic hardships for many families, thus affecting the standard of living. The rising costs of food items, goods, and services have created a challenging environment for many households, forcing them to struggle for basic survival. Many families and businesses are grappling with the consequences of fuel price hikes, which have strained their financial resources and disrupted their daily lives.

Table 2: Strategies households in Bayelsa State adopt to cope with the economic hardship caused by the removal of the fuel subsidy.

S/N	Items statement	SA (4)	A (3)	D (2)	SD(1)	Total	\bar{x}	Decision
1	Reduced spending on non-essential goods.	116	100	3	1	220		
	Weight of Responses	(464)	(300)	(6)	(1)	771	3.5	Agreed
2	Reduced expenditure on transportation.	114	101	2	3	220		
	Weight of Responses	(456)	(303)	(4)	(3)	766	3.4	Agreed
3	Reduced use of generator in the home.	119	92	4	5	220		
	Weight of Responses	(476)	(276)	(8)	(5)	765	3.4	Agreed
4	Engaging in farming activities.	113	96	6	5	220		
	Weight of Responses	(453)	(288)	(12)	(5)	757	3.4	Agreed
	Arithmetic Weighted Mean						3.42	
	Criterion Mean						2.50	

Source: Authors field data, 2024.

The data presented in Table 2 shows that the arithmetic weighted mean of 3.42 is greater than the criterion mean of 2.50. The results indicate that households in Bayelsa State have reduced their expenditures on transportation and non-essential goods and items, and use less fuel on their generators both in the home and in their business as a strategy to mitigate the economic hardship in the country. Additionally, most households in Bayelsa State now engage in farming activities to help mitigate the high cost of essential food items.

The findings from the questionnaire align with several interviews conducted on the strategies households in Bayelsa State are adopting to cope with the economic hardship caused by the removal of the fuel subsidy.

For instance, it was discovered during the interview that most families have prioritized their expenditure on essential food items due to the high cost of things in the country. Additionally, the high cost of foodstuffs in the market has prompted many families to engage in farming activities to cushion the high cost of foodstuffs in the market. The interview also revealed that most people now walk long distances before taking a tricycle or a taxi to reduce the cost of transportation.

The findings from the questionnaire and the oral interview clearly show that the removal of fuel subsidy has created agonizing economic hardship for Nigerians.

Table 3: Measures taken by the government to cushion the impact of fuel subsidy removal on households in Bayelsa State.

S/N	Items statement	SA (4)	A (3)	D (2)	SD(1)	Total	\bar{x}	Decision
1	Cash transfer given to vulnerable people.	1	0	97	121	220		
	Weight of Responses	(4)	(0)	(194)	(121)	319	1.4	Disagreed
2	Government has subsidized public transportation.	0	2	106	112	220		
	Weight of Responses	(0)	(6)	(212)	(112)	430	1.9	Disagreed
3	Foodstuff are provided for the poor.		1	111	108	220		
	Weight of Responses	(0)	(3)	(222)	(108)	333	1.5	Disagreed
4	Government has enforced price control on essential goods.	1	0	98	120	220		
	Weight of Responses	(4)	(0)	(196)	(120)	320	1.4	Disagreed
	Arithmetic Weighted Mean					1.55		
	Criterion Mean					2.50		

Source: Authors field data, 2024.

The data presented in Table 3 shows that the arithmetic weighted mean of 1.55 is less than the criterion mean of 2.50. The results from the findings indicate that the government has not taken any measures to cushion the impact of the fuel subsidy removal in Bayelsa State.

The findings from the questionnaire align with all the people interviewed regarding the measures taken by the government to cushion the impact of fuel subsidy removal on the masses. All the persons interviewed noted that the government has not provided any palliative to cushion the fuel subsidy removal in the country. They stated that even the compressed natural gas buses that the Federal Government promised to provide to ease transportation costs are not available. They noted that palliatives are only shared on television and the radio without getting to the people who really need them.

Conclusion

Fuel subsidy is one of the complex policies that have generated a lot of discussion in the country for the past two decades especially since the return of civil rule in 1999. It has brought the Nigerian government and the masses to a standoff with the citizens insisting for the continuation of the subsidy policy on the ground the removal of subsidy will inflict more economic hardship on the vulnerable people.

The removal of fuel subsidy in 2023 has created untold suffering on the masses as many families grapple to cope with the economic hardship brought by the removal of fuel subsidy. The study found out that the removal of fuel subsidy has negatively affected housed income, businesses as well as the standard of living in the country. The high cost of thing especially foodstuffs, goods and services including transportation has worsened the already high level of poverty in the country.

The failure of the Federal Government to roll out social safety policies to cushion the impact of the fuel subsidy removal has further exacerbated the level of poverty and suffering in the country.

Recommendations

- (i) **Provision of Compress Natural Gas Buses:** The Federal Government should roll out compress natural gas (CNG) buses across the country as well as subsidize public transportation to ease the high cost of transportation in the country. Also, CNG filling stations should be established across the 774 local government areas to make it accessible.
- (ii) **Establishment of CNG Conversion Centres:** Government should establish CNG conversion centres across the 36 states including and the Federal Capital Territory. Also, interest free loans should be given to vehicle owners and transporters willing to convert their vehicles to CNG.
- (iii) **Subsidy on Essential Foods:** The Federal Government should subsidize essential food items like rice, beans and flour to make them affordable and accessible to Nigerians. This will help cushion the economic hardship faced by the vulnerable people.
- (iv) **Cash Transfer to the Vulnerable:** Government should implement monthly cash transfer to the vulnerable to help alleviate the economic hardship in the country. Government should make use of the National Identity Card number to implement the monthly cash transfer.

REFERENCES

- Adeleke, A., Alabi, O., & Olawale, A. (2022). The impact of fuel subsidy on the Nigerian economy: An empirical analysis. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 13(5), 45-58.
- Adeyemi, A. (2012). Fuel subsidy removal and the rise in fuel prices in Nigeria. *Journal of Nigerian Affairs*, 15(3), 25-40.
- Ahiuma, V.Y. (2024). Distress as harsh economy forces shutdown of over 50 firms. Vanguard. <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2024/08/distress-as-harsh-economy-forces-shutdown-of-over-50-firms/>
- Aiana, D (2025). Marketers forged 24 documents to claim subsidy payments – Ex-EFCC boss. <https://punchng.com/marketers-forged-24-documents-to-claim-subsidy-payments-ex-efcc-boss/>
- Ajayi, S. (2023). Impact of fuel subsidy removal on household economics in Nigeria. *Journal of African Economic Studies*, 12(1), 45-60.
- Akpan, U. (2025). Petrol subsidy removal generates \$84bn, 40 roads – Report. Vanguard. [file:///C:/Users/Esther/Desktop/FUEL%20SUBSIDY/Petrol%20subsidy%20removal%20generates%20\\$84bn,%2040%20roads%20%E2%80%93%20Report%20-%20Vanguard%20News.htm](file:///C:/Users/Esther/Desktop/FUEL%20SUBSIDY/Petrol%20subsidy%20removal%20generates%20$84bn,%2040%20roads%20%E2%80%93%20Report%20-%20Vanguard%20News.htm)
- Akpan, U., Egwuatu, P., Ahiuma, V.Y., Esiedesa, O., Kolawole, Y., Mosadomi, E.S.,... Oritse, O. (2024). Anger trails rise in pump price of petrol to N855/litre. Vanguard. <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2024/09/anger-trails-rise-in-pump-price-of-petrol-to-n855-litre/>
- Amaize, E., Arubi, E. and Omafuaire, A. (2012). Fuel subsidy protest spreads to Warri, Effurun. Vanguard. <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2012/01/fuel-subsidy-protest-spreads-to-warri-effurun-2/>
- Edu, S., Ahmed, J., Aderoboye, A., & Afolabi, K. (2023). Subsidy: Commuters stranded as transporters down tool. *The Hope*. https://www.thehopenewspaper.com/subsidy-commuters-stranded-as-transporters-down-tool/#google_vignette
- Igbokwe-Ibeto, C.J, Ewuim, N.C & Agbodike, F.C (2015). Nigerian government and oil subsidy regime: A horn of dilemma
- International Institute for Sustainable Development (2016). Compensation mechanisms for fuel subsidy removal in Nigeria.
- Kojima, M., & Bacon, R. (2009). "Explaining fuel price differences across countries." World Bank energy sector management assistance program.
- Nwankwo, F. (2023). Rising costs and household income in Bayelsa: A study post-fuel subsidy removal. *Bayelsa State Economic Review*, 5(2), 77-90.

- Ogunfowora, O. (2022). Economic implications of fuel subsidy removal in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Economic Policy*, 10(3), 123-138.
- Okerinde, A. (2023). Subsidy Removal: Things seem anxious, uncertain — Tinubu. <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2023/07/subsidy-removal-things-seem-anxious-uncertain-tinubu/>
- Onuoha, F. C. (2017). Fuel subsidy in Nigeria: Dispelling the myths, sustaining the realities, *African Journal of Economic and Sustainable Development*, 6(1), 1-21.
- Onyeizugbe, C & Onwuka, E.M (2012). Fuel Subsidy Removal as an Imperative for Enhancing Business Development in Nigeria. *VRSD International Journal of Business and Management Research*. 2 (9), 454-461
- Ori, O.E, Obidebube,E.J & Obongha, R. (2023). Fuel Subsidy Debate: The Nigerian Experience from 1999- 2023. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Accounting, Economics and Business Perspectives*, 7(2), 180-191.
- Oyetunde, O. (2012). The implications of the fuel subsidy removal for Nigeria’s social fabric. *International Journal of African Studies*,18(1), 45-62.
- Schwartz, G. & Clements, B. (1999). Government subsidies. *Journal of Economic Surveys*.13 (2), 119 – 147.
- Steenblik, R. (2006). A Subsidy Primer. Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD).
- Udeme, A. (2025). Petrol subsidy removal generates \$84bn, 40 roads – report. *Vanguard*. <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2025/06/petrol-subsidy-removal-generates-84bn-40-roads-report/>
- Ujah, E. (2023). Use subsidy savings to lessen suffering, World Bank tells FG. *Vanguard*. <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2023/06/world-bank-to-fg-distribute-subsidy-savings-as-palliatives-to-nigerians/>
- United Nations Development Programme. (2023). The role of fuel subsidies in achieving Sustainable Development Goals. <https://www.undp.org/publications/role-fuel-subsidies>
- World Bank. (2010). *Fuel subsidies and poverty reduction*. <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/2440>
- World Bank. (2021). Fuel Subsidies and the Green Transition. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/feature/2021/06/30/fuel-subsidies-and-the-green>